

1 **Performance of a polypropylene membrane contactor for the recovery of dissolved**
2 **methane from anaerobic effluents: mass transfer evaluation, long-term operation and**
3 **cleaning strategies**

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12 **Abstract**

13 A polypropylene membrane contactor was used for the recovery of dissolved methane from an
14 anaerobic reactor effluent. Effect of operational parameters, operation mode and fouling on
15 long-term operation was studied using vacuum pressure or N₂ as sweep gas. Results were
16 analyzed based on the mass transfer estimations. Lower performance was observed in the shell-
17 side mode due to the lower liquid velocity and the probable channeling. Membrane pore wetting
18 was observed with the increase in Q_L in the vacuum-pressure mode. This was confirmed with
19 mass transfer resistance analysis, resulting in an estimated wetted pore fraction of between 0.25
20 and 0.53. The highest removal efficiencies were obtained with the liquid flowing in the lumen
21 side and sweep-gas operation (between 98% and 67% for Q_L between 4.1 and 27.2 L h⁻¹), with
22 negligible effect of the N₂ flow rate. In the long-term operation, the impact of membrane fouling
23 was less intense in the lumen side, with longer operation time and more reversible fouling. A
24 complete characterization of the fouling based on water sample analysis concluded that both
25 inorganic and organic foulants were present, probably with higher biofouling presence. A
26 combination of water and chemical cleanings resulted in a recommended protocol based on
27 daily water cleaning.

28
29 **Keywords**

30 Anaerobic reactor; fouling; mass transfer; membrane contactor; methane degassing

1. Introduction

Anaerobic reactors for the wastewater treatments generate a methane-rich biogas, which can be used in combustion for the production of heat and/or electricity. Even though the low solubility of methane in water, residual dissolved methane (D-CH₄) is often present in the final water effluent, especially in anaerobic treatments at sub-mesophilic and psychrophilic temperatures (<25 °C) due to the increase in gas solubility at low temperatures [1]. Increase in greenhouse gas diffuse emissions, loss of energy source and generation of potential explosive atmospheres when discharged into closed vessels or sewers are the main problems when managing these effluents. Thus, its recovery/removal is necessary for economic, environmental and security reasons. The treatment technologies for gas desorption from anaerobic waters include spray aeration, packed towers, tray aerators, diffuse aeration, and membrane contactors [2]. The use of membrane contactors is a commercially available mature technology for applications such as O₂ or CO₂ removal, among others [3]. However, its application for the removal D-CH₄ from anaerobic effluents is still at research/pilot level. From the first promising results [4-8], the number of published papers has grown in recent years [9-14], demonstrating the interest of scientific community in this technology. However, some practical implications, such as the long-term stability of membrane contactors and the optimum driving force (vacuum/sweep gas) are still scarcely studied, and further research is needed.

Membrane contactors offer many advantages over conventional technologies [2]; however, the presence of the membrane introduces an additional mass transfer resistance. Depending on membrane material, the nature of the liquid phase and transmembrane pressure, the membrane pores may be occupied by liquid, corresponding to the so-called wetted operation, which strongly decreases the permeate flux. Measures to prevent the wetting problem may include the increase in the hydrophobicity of the membrane by increasing the contact angle between the liquid and the membrane [14]. The surface tension of the liquid phase also plays an important role. The presence of organic compounds may decrease the surface tension of solutions, which decreases the breakthrough pressure, leading to a rapid increase in membrane wetting. The wetting phenomenon is an effect widely studied in the CO₂ absorption using organic absorbents [15,16], and water-based absorbents [17-19]. In the application of membrane contactors for degassing water solutions, the wetting phenomenon is also reported to be associated with the increase in liquid flow rate [10,20].

The driving force for D-CH₄ removal can be obtained by applying vacuum or using a sweep gas on the gas side. For the recovery and reuse of the downstream gas phase, methane concentration in the recovered gas for commercial microturbines should be higher than 35% [21]. To achieve such a concentration, sweep-gas mode at low gas-to-liquid flow-rate ratio (G/L) was proposed [11]; however, this induced an increase in gas phase mass transfer resistance, and so a reduction in the D-CH₄ recovery efficiency. Vacuum operation overcomes this problem and some authors recommend it [12,22]. However, vacuum operation is less energetically favorable than use of sweep gas, and higher pressure difference between gas and liquid phase could induce pore wetting [10].

Loss of performance due to membrane fouling is one of the main problems encountered when coupling biological reactors and membrane technologies. In this regard, natural organic matter related to microbial and extracellular polymer substances has been described as the major type of foulant in biological wastewater treatment units [23]. Fortunately, membrane contactors are less sensitive to fouling, since there is no convective flow through the membrane pores causing

1 concentration polarization, as in the pressure-driven membrane process of membrane
2 bioreactors. Clogging due to suspended particles coming from the regular discharge of surplus
3 biomass particles may be a major concern in membrane contactors, and prefiltration is
4 necessary. Suspended solid concentration in anaerobic effluents usually are in the range 100 –
5 300 mg L⁻¹. The particle size analysis of the effluent of a laboratory-scale anaerobic reactor
6 operated under similar conditions than the one of this study revealed that 60-85% of solids were
7 higher than 300 μm, so susceptible of generate rapid clogging of the hollow fiber membrane
8 contactors, especially when liquid flows inside the fibers [24]. Also, protein adsorption (organic
9 fouling) and salt precipitation (inorganic fouling) onto the membrane surface can be involved as
10 causes of fouling [25,26]. For the industrial application of the technology, operational and
11 cleaning strategies optimization are of crucial interest for the prevention of the use of cleaning
12 chemicals to ensure an economically feasible operation with a long stable life of the system.

13 Few studies can be found in the literature that evaluate the long-term operation of membrane
14 contactors for methane degassing. Bandara et al. [5,6] indicated that membrane fouling of the
15 contactor was insignificant for their long-term experiments with a lab-scale UASB reactor
16 (>30days). Sethunga et al. [14] operated a modified PVDF hollow fiber membrane contactor
17 with synthetic water containing dissolved biogas for 10 days to investigate the resistance to pore
18 wetting, and concluded that the fluctuation of the methane flux was less than 10%. In our
19 previous work [12] with a PDMS membrane contactor, long-term experiments in lumen-side
20 and shell-side mode treating an anaerobic effluent included both intermediate water and
21 chemical cleaning and the characterization of organic and inorganic foulants. Results
22 highlighted the importance of implementing a prevention strategy of membrane fouling, based
23 preferably on the use of water cleaning. The polypropylene membrane contactor of this study
24 showed higher removal efficiency than the PDMS in short-term experiments when pore wetting
25 phenomenon was not observed [10]. For the industrial application of the technology, it is crucial
26 not only the short-term efficiency but also the performance in long-term and continuous
27 operation, so the present work extend and complement our previous studies and allow
28 comparison of response of membrane materials from the fouling perspective.

29 In this context, the aim of this work is to assess the performance of a polypropylene membrane
30 contactor for the removal of dissolved methane from the effluent of a laboratory-scale expanded
31 granular sludge-bed anaerobic reactor. Influence of the operational parameters (liquid flow rate,
32 vacuum pressure and sweep gas flow rate) on the methane removal efficiency was studied in
33 short-term experiments. An analysis of the results based on mass transfer evaluation is also
34 presented. In the present work, our previous study [10] is broadened, with a greater range of
35 operation conditions, including an estimation of the mass transfer resistances with literature
36 correlations. As a special novelty, to study the impact of the fouling on removal efficiency,
37 long-term experiments in the lumen side and shell side were performed. Research efforts were
38 aimed at characterizing the fouling and optimizing the cleaning strategies, focusing on the
39 application of the technology.

40 **2. Materials and methods**

41 *2.1. Experimental set-up and operation*

42 The anaerobic effluent used in the degassing experiments came from a laboratory-scale
43 expanded granular sludge-bed (EGSB) anaerobic reactor operated at 25 °C. Granular anaerobic
44 sludge (4 L) from the wastewater treatment plant of a local brewery (Font Salem, El Puig) was
45 used for inoculation. The reactor treated 8 L d⁻¹ of synthetic wastewater polluted with ethanol

1 with an organic load rate of 30 kg chemical oxygen demand (COD) m⁻³ d⁻¹. The sludge bed was
 2 kept expanded with a recirculation up-flow velocity of 10.7 m h⁻¹. A liquid-gas separator device
 3 was placed at the top of the reactor. The gas outlet was connected to a gas wash bottle
 4 containing sodium hydroxide solution to remove carbon dioxide and hydrogen sulfide from the
 5 biogas. Biogas composition of the headspace of the bioreactor was measured from samples
 6 taken prior to the gas wash bottle. The methane flow rate was monitored periodically with a gas
 7 flowmeter (MGC-10 PMMA, Ritter, Germany) and the pH and conductivity with a
 8 multiparameter sensor (pH/Cond 340i WTW, Germany). Alkalinity, volatile fatty acids (VFA),
 9 COD, and nutrient concentration in the inlet and outlet of the reactor were analyzed according to
 10 standard methods [27]. A detailed description of the system and procedure can be found
 11 elsewhere [28,29].

12 A commercial hollow-fiber membrane contactor with polypropylene (PP) fibers was used for D-
 13 CH₄ removal (1×5.5 MiniModule, Liqui-Cel, Membrana GmbH, Germany), connected to the
 14 recirculation stream of the bioreactor, with similar composition to the final effluent. The main
 15 characteristics of the membrane contactor are presented in Table 1. The anaerobic stream was
 16 pumped through the contactor using a peristaltic pump (Watson-Marlow, USA). A 40 μm
 17 prefilter was placed prior to the contactor, in order to prevent the membrane contactor clogging
 18 with particulate matter from the bioreactor. Liquid pressures at the inlet and outlet of the
 19 membrane contactor were measured using a portable manometer MP112 (Kimo, Spain). A
 20 complete scheme of the EGSB reactor and the membrane contactor is presented in Figure 1.

21
 22 **Figure 1.** Scheme of the set-up of the EGSB reactor and degassing membrane contactor

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1 **Table 1.** Polypropylene membrane contactor specifications and operational conditions.

Module inner diameter, m	0.025
Module length, m	0.176
Number of fibres	2300
Effective fibre length, L , m	0.1397
Inner diameter, μm	220
Outer diameter, μm	300
Fibre wall thickness, l , μm	40
Inner area, A_i , m^2	0.180
Outer area, A_o , m^2	0.303
Pore radius, r_p , μm	0.02
Shell inner diameter, m	0.025
Packing fraction, ϕ	0.33
Porosity, ε	0.4
Tortuosity, τ	1.4
Lumen side volume, m^3	16×10^{-6}
Shell side volume, m^3	25×10^{-6}
Max. liquid flow-rate, Q_L , L h^{-1}	30
Typical sweep gas flow-rate, Q_{N_2} , L h^{-1}	26.0-800

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2.2. Operation of the membrane contactor

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Comparison of the main parameters affecting the performance of the contactor was carried out in 39 short-term experiments of around 90 min, the minimum time necessary to assure stable operation [10]. In this previous work [10], some performance results of these short-term experiments were used, in order to compare a PDMS (nonporous) and a PP (porous) membrane contactor for D-CH₄ removal. We have broadened the study to delve into the effect of the operational conditions on the PP contactor performance. A total of 20 vacuum pressure experiments (vacuum pump N026.3.AT.18, KNF Neuberger, Germany) were carried out with vacuum pressures of -140, -500 and -800 mbar, with the liquid flowing through the lumen (Lumen-Side mode, LS) and through the shell (Shell-Side mode, SS). Likewise, a total of 19 countercurrent sweep-gas experiments were carried out using high purity N₂ (>99.8%, Carburos Metálicos, SA). Sweep-gas flow was fixed in the range 26–800 L N₂ h⁻¹, and it was introduced using a mass flow controller (Bronkhorst Hi-Tec, The Netherlands). Both in the vacuum and in the sweep-gas experiments, liquid flow was also varied between 4.1 and 27.2 L h⁻¹. Operational conditions were fixed in the range of values recommended by the supplier in order to elucidate their effect on the D-CH₄ removal efficiency. Performance of the contactor was evaluated by analyzing D-CH₄ in water samples at the inlet (C_{L1} , mg L⁻¹) and outlet (C_{L2} , mg L⁻¹) of the module at the end of the experiment, and the removal efficiency (RE,%) was calculated:

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$$RE = \frac{C_{L1} - C_{L2}}{C_{L1}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

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During the short-term experiments, a daily cleaning with deionized water in countercurrent flow was applied for 30 min. Likewise, a control experiment was repeated periodically to check that the RE was not altered over the whole period, accounting for 3510 h of operation in LS mode and 1620 h in SS mode without loss of efficiency due to fouling.

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1 Fouling of the membranes is one of the main operational problems that membrane technologies
2 must face. In order to evaluate the response of the system to continuous operation, two long-
3 term experiments were carried out with N₂ flow rate of 26 L h⁻¹ as sweep gas: one with the
4 liquid through the lumen and another through the shell, with a liquid flow rate of 20.4 L h⁻¹.
5 Follow-up of the performance was carried out by analyzing the D-CH₄ every 2–3 h of operation.
6 Water and N₂ flow rates were checked daily. Cleaning of the contactor was performed only
7 when RE decreased. Two different cleaning protocols were used: (1) countercurrent deionized
8 water cleaning for 2 h, as a soft conventional protocol; (2) a chemical cleaning applied when the
9 water cleaning was ineffective. The chemical cleaning used, recommended by the supplier [30],
10 consisted first of a countercurrent flow of a 2% (w/w) sodium hydroxide solution for 2 h in a
11 closed loop, then a water cleaning for 10 min, followed by a flow of 10% (w/w) citric acid
12 solution for 2 h in closed loop, and a final water cleaning for 10 min. Solutions resulting from
13 the chemical cleaning were analyzed to characterize the nature of the fouling and to optimize
14 the cleaning protocol.

15 The presence of biofouling was elucidated with an experiment consisting of flowing 250 mL of
16 a solution that mimicked the feed of the anaerobic reactor through the membrane contactor in a
17 closed loop for 4 h at 20 L h⁻¹, without application of vacuum pressure or sweep gas. The
18 solution was composed of 800 mg COD/L of ethanol, with alkalinity and macro- and micro-
19 nutrients according to Lafita et al. [27]. The COD concentration of the feed solution was
20 analyzed at the beginning and end of the experiment. The experiment was performed when the
21 membrane was fouled, and a blank test (cleaned membrane) was carried out for comparison
22 purposes.

23 2.3. Sampling and analytical methods

24 Water samples were taken from the recirculation of the bioreactor (before the 40 μm prefilter),
25 from the inlet (after filtration) and from the outlet of the membrane contactor with a three-way
26 valve system. A complete characterization of water samples was performed to determine the D-
27 CH₄ removal efficiency and to evaluate the change of the water quality and its potential
28 influence on the fouling appearance and mechanisms.

29 D-CH₄ was determined using a headspace method as described elsewhere [12]. Briefly, 50 mL
30 of water were shaken in a closed vial of 125 mL for 3 h at 25 °C. After equilibration, the
31 headspace gas concentration (C_{GH}, mg L⁻¹) was analyzed by gas chromatography (Agilent GC
32 7820A, Spain). The D-CH₄ in liquid phase (C_L, mg L⁻¹) was calculated as:

$$C_L = \frac{C_{GH} (V_{GH} + V_L/H)}{V_L} \quad (2)$$

33 where V_{GH} is the headspace gas volume, V_L is the liquid volume, and H is the dimensionless
34 Henry's law constant (defined as gas per liquid concentration, C_{GH} = H · C_L).

35 Soluble COD and solid content of water samples were determined according to the Standard
36 Methods for the Examination of Water and Wastewater [26]. Soluble Total Organic Carbon
37 (TOC) in water was measured using a total organic carbon analyzer (TOC-VCSH, Shimadzu
38 Corporation, Japan). VFA and alkalinity of centrifuged samples were determined according to
39 the 5-point acid-base titration method, using a potentiometer titrator (848 Titrino Plus,
40 Metrohm, Switzerland). Turbidity of water samples was determined using a turbidimeter
41 according to EN ISO 7027 (Turbiquant® 1500 IT/T, Merck, Germany). pH and conductivity of

liquid samples was measured (pH/Cond 340i WTW, Germany). Concentration of different cations (Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , NH_4^+ , Na^+ , and K^+) and anions (SO_4^{2-} , NO_3^- , PO_4^{3-} , Cl^-) in liquid samples were measured with an ionic chromatograph (883 Basic IC Plus, Metrohm, Switzerland) equipped with Metrosep C4–250/4.0 and Metrosep A Supp 3 columns. The soluble content of polysaccharides and proteins of water samples were determined by the colorimetric methods proposed by Dubois et al. [31] and Lowry et al. [32], respectively. Biogas production was determined using a biogas volumetric measuring device (MGC-10 PMMA, Ritter, Germany), and biogas composition using a gas chromatograph (Agilent GC 7820A, Spain).

2.4. Mass transfer calculations

The experimental overall mass transfer coefficient (K_{Lexp} , m s^{-1}) of methane was calculated from the mass balance applied at the liquid phase in the membrane contactor by the following differential expression [33]:

$$Q_L \frac{dC}{dA} = -K_{Lexp}(C_L - C_L^*) \quad (3)$$

where Q_L is the liquid flow rate ($\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$), A is the interfacial area (m^2), and C_L^* is the concentration of methane in the liquid phase (mg L^{-1}) in equilibrium with the gas phase calculated from Henry's law ($C_L^* = C_G/H$).

Integration of equation (3) through the membrane contactor (1:inlet, 2: outlet) results in:

$$K_{Lexp} = -\frac{Q_L}{A} \ln \left(\frac{C_{L2} - C_L^*}{C_{L1} - C_L^*} \right) \quad (4)$$

The overall mass transfer resistance (R_{ov} , s m^{-3}) is expressed as the sum of the three individual resistances in series in the system: the liquid, membrane and gas mass transfer resistances (R_L , R_m and R_G , respectively). A schematic of the mass transfer resistances for the membrane contactor in gas desorption is included in Appendix A. For the driving force based on the aqueous phase concentration [33]:

$$R_{ov} = \frac{1}{K_L A_L} = \frac{1}{k_L A_L} + \frac{1}{H k_m A_{ml}} + \frac{1}{H k_G A_G} = R_L + R_m + R_G \quad (5)$$

where K_L is the overall mass transfer coefficient based on liquid driving force (m s^{-1}), k_L , k_m and k_G the individual mass transfer coefficients of the liquid, membrane and gas (m s^{-1}), respectively, A_L the membrane surface in contact with the liquid (0.222 m^2 for lumen-side liquid flow and 0.303 m^2 for shell-side liquid flow), A_{ml} the logarithmic mean membrane surface based on a cylindrical body (0.260 m^2), A_G the membrane surface in contact with the gas (m^2), and H the equilibrium partition coefficient of the solute gas in between the gas and liquid phases (Henry coefficient).

Individual mass transfer coefficients can be estimated using correlations in the form:

$$Sh \propto Re^\alpha Sc^\beta Gz^\gamma f(\text{geometry})$$

1 where Sh , Re , Sc and Gz are the Sherwood, Reynolds, Schmidt and Graetz numbers,
2 respectively, and f is a function of the geometry. Table 2 summarizes the equations used in this
3 study for the estimation of the mass transfer coefficients, which are among the most common
4 correlations used for the estimation of coefficients of the fluids (liquid or gas) flowing in the
5 lumen or shell side of a hollow-fiber membrane contactor [33].

6 When fluid flows through the lumen side, the Lvque solution (equation 11) [34] was
7 considered for the estimation of coefficients. In contrast to the lumen-side flow, shell-side flow
8 is not fully understood. A number of correlations can be found in the literature, but none is
9 applicable to a wide range of systems as is the Lvque equation [33]. For the coefficient of the
10 fluid in the shell side in parallel flow, two correlations are considered in this study. Equation 13
11 was proposed by Prasad and Sirkar [35], and it includes the packing fraction of the contactor.
12 Equation 15 was proposed by Dahuron and Cussler [36], and it is characterized by a Reynolds
13 number exponent deviating from the expected value of 0.6, maybe due to the different
14 channeling around the fibers, according to the authors.

15 The mass transfer coefficient of the membrane (k_m , $m\ s^{-1}$) was estimated by considering the
16 effective diffusion of the transferred species in the gas phase ($D_{G,eff}$, $m^2\ s^{-1}$) [37,38], which is
17 calculated by considering the two types of diffusion distinguished in the porous structure:
18 molecular diffusion ($D_{G,m}$, $m^2\ s^{-1}$) and Knudsen diffusion ($D_{G,Kn}$, $m^2\ s^{-1}$) (equations 16 to 19).
19 Molecular diffusion is determined by the interactions of the molecules [39], and Knudsen
20 diffusion by the interactions of molecules with the pore walls, which become significant for
21 small pores ($d < 0.1\ \mu m$) [40]. Values of the diffusion coefficients of methane in water, nitrogen
22 and air used in this study are summarized in Table 3.

1 **Table 2.** Literature correlations for the estimation of the mass transfer coefficients in a porous
2 membrane (k_m), and in the liquid or gas phase (k_L or k_G) when flowing in the lumen or shell side
3 of a hollow-fiber membrane contactor.

Dimensionless numbers			
Sherwood number, Sh	$Sh = \frac{k d}{D}$	(6)	d : fibre diameter, m d_e : equivalent diameter, m
Reynolds number, Re	$Re = \frac{d \rho v}{\mu}$	(7)	D : diffusion coefficient in the liquid or gas phase, $m^2 s^{-1}$
Schmidt number, Sc	$Sc = \frac{\mu}{\rho D}$	(8)	$D_{G,eff}$: effective diffusion of the transferred specie in the gas phase, $m^2 s^{-1}$
Graetz number, Gz	$Gz = \frac{d^2 v}{D L}$	(9)	$D_{G,Kn}$: Knudsen diffusion, $m^2 s^{-1}$ $D_{G,m}$: molecular diffusion, $m^2 s^{-1}$
Flow through the lumen			
Leveque equation [34]	$Sh = 1.62 Gz^{1/3} \quad (\text{for } Gz > 4)$	(10)	k : individual mass transfer coefficient, $m s^{-1}$
	$k_{L \text{ or } G} = \frac{D}{d} 1.62 \left(\frac{d^2 v}{L D} \right)^{1/3}$	(11)	k_L : liquid phase mass transfer coefficient, $m s^{-1}$ k_G : gas phase mass transfer coefficient, $m s^{-1}$
Parallel flow through the shell			
Prasad and Sirkar (1988) [35]	$Sh = \beta \frac{d_e (1 - \phi)}{L} Re^{0.6} Sc^{0.33}$	(12)	k_m : membrane mass transfer coefficient, $m s^{-1}$
	$k_{L \text{ or } G} = D \beta \frac{(1 - \phi)}{L} \left(\frac{d_e v \rho}{\mu} \right)^{0.6} \left(\frac{\mu}{\rho D} \right)^{0.33}$	(13)	l : membrane thickness, m L : fibre length, m M_{CH_4} : molecular weight of methane M_{gas} : molecular weight of the gas (air or N_2)
	for $0 < Re < 500$ and $0.04 < \phi < 400$ $\beta = 5.8$ for hydrophobic membranes $\beta = 6.1$ for hydrophilic membranes		P : gas side pressure, Pa r_p : membrane porous radius, m T : temperature, K
Dahuron and Cussler (1988) [36]	$Sh = 8 \left(\frac{Re d_e}{L} \right) Sc^{0.33}$	(14)	
	$k_{L \text{ or } G} = 8 D \left(\frac{d_e v \rho}{\mu L} \right) \left(\frac{\mu}{\rho D} \right)^{0.33}$	(15)	
Porous Membrane			
Qi and Cussler (1985) [37]	$k_m = \frac{D_{G,eff} \varepsilon}{\tau l}$	(16)	β : empirical coefficient ε : membrane porosity
Kreulen et al (1993) [38]	$D_{G,eff} = \left(\frac{1}{D_{G,m}} + \frac{1}{D_{G,Kn}} \right)^{-1}$	(17)	ρ : density, $g m^{-3}$ μ : liquid or gas viscosity, $g m^{-1} s^{-1}$ v : liquid or gas velocity, $m s^{-1}$
Fuller et al (1969) [41]	$D_{G,m} = \frac{0.01013 T^{1.75} \left(\frac{1}{M_{gas}} + \frac{1}{M_{CH_4}} \right)^{1/2}}{P \left[(\Sigma v)_{gas}^{1/3} + (\Sigma v)_{CH_4}^{1/3} \right]^2}$	(18)	μ : viscosity, $g m^{-1} s^{-1}$ ϕ : fibre packing fraction τ : membrane tortuosity
Cussler (1984) [40]	$D_{G,Kn} = 97.0 r_p \left(\frac{T}{M_{CH_4}} \right)^{1/2}$	(19)	Σv : special atomic diffusion volumes of the gas and methane, from [41]

1 **Table 3.** Diffusion coefficient of methane in water, nitrogen and air at 25 °C and 1 bar.

Phase	Diffusion coefficient, D , $\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$	Reference
Water	$1.76 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$	[42]
Nitrogen	$2.19 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$	[42]
Air	$1.76 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$	[41]

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3 **3. Results and discussion**

4 *3.1. Bioreactor start-up and operation: evolution of methane concentration in the system*

5 The start-up of the bioreactor was carried out with a gradual increase in the organic loading rate
6 (OLR) from 4 to 30 kg COD $\text{m}^{-3} \text{d}^{-1}$, resulting in six operating phases (from A to F, Table 4).
7 Ethanol RE was higher than 97% from the beginning, and values of 99% were recorded after
8 only 2 days of operation, which was maintained during the whole operation period. pH,
9 alkalinity and VFA concentrations were monitored daily during the start-up (phase A to E),
10 resulting in average value of 7.6 ± 0.2 , $2788 \pm 294 \text{ mg CaCO}_3 \text{ L}^{-1}$ and $13 \pm 24 \text{ mg CH}_3\text{COOH}$
11 L^{-1} , respectively. The high RE, stable pH and low VFA concentration indicated a smooth start-
12 up of the reactor. Similar results were obtained during the operation at the maximum OLR of
13 30 kg COD $\text{m}^{-3} \text{d}^{-1}$ in phase F, in which the membrane contactor was connected for the removal
14 of D- CH_4 from water. Average pH, alkalinity and VFA concentrations were 7.4 ± 0.2 ,
15 $2821 \pm 337 \text{ mg CaCO}_3 \text{ L}^{-1}$, and $51 \pm 45 \text{ mg CH}_3\text{COOH L}^{-1}$, respectively. Similar results have
16 been reported in previous experiments [27].

17 Methane content in the biogas generated in the reactor (% CH_4 exp.) was also monitored, and the
18 results are presented in Table 4. Values were greater than 88% from phase A to E, higher than
19 those estimated from stoichiometric ethanol anaerobic degradation (75% CH_4). This higher
20 methane content is associated with the pH and bicarbonate alkalinity concentration in the
21 system. From the experimentally measured pH, alkalinity and VFA concentrations, the
22 theoretical methane content (% CH_4 est.) was estimated, assuming that CO_2 and CH_4 account for
23 100% of the biogas composition (measured H_2S concentration < 140 ppm) [43]. Equations used
24 for estimation are included in Appendix A. The estimates are compared in Table 4 with the
25 experimental results, and as can be seen, good agreement between estimated and experimental
26 values was obtained, with relative errors lower than 3%.

27 D- CH_4 concentration in the water (C_{L1} , mg L^{-1}) was monitored, and results are shown in Table
28 4. The D- CH_4 concentration increased gradually with the OLR, so with biogas production. The
29 methane oversaturation factor in water has been calculated as the ratio between the experimental
30 and equilibrium D- CH_4 concentration with the gas phase (C_{L1}/C_{Leq}), and it has been included in
31 the table. Equilibrium concentration of methane in the water of the bioreactor (C_{Leq} , mg L^{-1}) was
32 calculated with the experimental methane content in the biogas (% CH_4 exp.) assuming a
33 Henry's law constant of 29.55 for methane at 25 °C [44]. In the first phase (A), D- CH_4
34 concentration was below the equilibrium value, but achieved values slightly higher than the
35 equilibrium for phases between B and D (OLR = 9.2–20.0 kg COD $\text{m}^{-3} \text{d}^{-1}$). For OLR higher
36 than 27 kg COD $\text{m}^{-3} \text{d}^{-1}$, the oversaturation factor showed values between 1.45 and 1.96. During
37 phase F, when the membrane contactor was connected, the biogas generated had an average
38 composition of $82 \pm 3\% \text{ CH}_4$, $18 \pm 7\% \text{ CO}_2$, and $110 \pm 16 \text{ ppm H}_2\text{S}$. The average concentration
39 of D- CH_4 in the water effluent entering the membrane contactor was $31.12 \pm 3.1 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$. This
40 value corresponded to an oversaturation factor of 1.72 ± 0.23 . The methane oversaturation in

1 water effluents is frequently observed in laboratory and industrial bioreactors [45], and it could
 2 enhance the methane mass transfer coefficient in membrane contactors [9,12].

3 In Figure 2, the oversaturation factor is plotted against the daily methane production in the
 4 biogas (Q_{CH_4}) for all the OLRs. A relationship can be inferred from the results, due to the
 5 increase in the D- CH_4 concentration with Q_{CH_4} . The equilibrium D- CH_4 concentration (C_{Leq})
 6 decreased slightly due to the decrease in % CH_{4exp} (from 17 to 21 mg D- $CH_4 L^{-1}$), which also had
 7 a positive effect in the oversaturation factor. However, the main parameter affecting the
 8 oversaturation is the increase in D- CH_4 concentration with the daily methane production.

9 **Table 4.** Methane content in the biogas (% CH_4) and in the water effluent (C_{LI}) of the anaerobic
 10 reactor during the start-up (Phase A–E) and stable operation conditions (Phase F).

Phase (days)	OLR (kgCOD m ⁻³ d ⁻¹)	Day	pH	Alkalinity (mg CaCO ₃ L ⁻¹)	Volatile fatty acids (mg CH ₃ COOH L ⁻¹)	%CH ₄ exp.	C _{LI} (mg CH ₄ L ⁻¹)	Oversaturat. Factor (C _{LI} /C _{Leq})	%CH ₄ est.	Rel. Error (%)
A (0-6)	4.2±0.3	2	8.0±0.1	2571±25	0	97±1	13.5±3.6	0.63	96	1.6
B (6-16)	9.2±0.9	9	7.6±0.1	1351±36	0	95±1	25.1±0.7	1.19	94	0.8
		12	7.6±0.2	2564±18	37±8	91±2	20.2±1.6	1.00	90	1.4
C (16-21)	11.7±0.2	16	7.6±0.1	2762±12	41±6	90±2	20.6±0.9	1.03	89	1.6
		20	7.6±0.1	1966±33	0	91±3	24.5±1.5	1.22	93	2.1
D (21-23)	20.0±0.4	22	7.5±0.1	2872±41	0	88±1	20.5±1.3	1.05	85	3.0
E (23-29)	26.8±0.2	28	7.5±0.1	2974±23	6±2	88±2	32.0±2.9	1.64	86	2.6
F (29-88)	30.2±0.5	48	7.5±0.1	2944±25	42±7	84±2	27.0±0.6	1.45	86	1.9
		70	7.5±0.2	3037±24	80±11	83±3	33.6±2.9	1.83	83	0.5
		73	7.5±0.1	2832±11	127±16	83±2	30.2±2.7	1.63	86	2.7
		87	7.4±0.2	3266±17	110±9	77±1	33.5±0.9	1.96	78	1.2

11

12 **Figure 2.** Variation of the oversaturation factor of methane in the anaerobic effluent with the
 13 daily methane production in the bioreactor
 14
 15

16 **3.2. Parameters affecting the performance of the membrane contactor**

1 Short-term experiments (time of operation ≤ 90 min) were carried out to characterize the
 2 performance of the PP membrane contactor both in the LS and SS mode at different operational
 3 conditions. Figure 3 shows the results as D-CH₄ RE versus liquid flow rate (Q_L) for the vacuum
 4 and sweep-gas operation. For the complete set of experiments, RE decreased with an increase in
 5 liquid flow rate, as frequently reported [9,11,12,14]. In the sweep-gas operation (Figure 3b), the
 6 decrease in RE was more pronounced when the liquid flowed in the lumen, with values ranging
 7 from around 98% to 67% for Q_L values between 4.1 and 27.2 L h⁻¹, respectively. When the N₂
 8 flow rate was varied in the range 26–800 L N₂ h⁻¹, the performance of the system was
 9 unchanged and the RE nearly overlapped for all the liquid flow rates tested, suggesting that the
 10 gas phase mass transfer resistance was negligible. This indicates that the concentration of each
 11 transfer species in the gas phase was small enough to consider that the concentration in liquid
 12 phase in equilibrium with the gas phase was negligible compared to the actual concentration in
 13 the liquid phase ($C_L \gg C_L^*$). In the vacuum operation (Figure 3a), for every liquid flow rate
 14 tested the RE increased with the increase in the vacuum applied, in the range from –140 to –800
 15 mbar vacuum pressure (P_{vac}), suggesting that the concentration gradient (i.e. the driving force)
 16 increased with the P_{vac} , favoring D-CH₄ recovery. The maximum RE of 93% was achieved at
 17 the highest vacuum pressure (–800 mbar) and the lowest liquid flow rate (4.1 L h⁻¹) in lumen-
 18 side mode.

19

20 **Figure 3.** D-CH₄ removal efficiency versus liquid flow rate for the a) Vacuum operation (Δ –
 21 800 mbar; \circ –500 mbar; \diamond –140 mbar) and b) Sweep-gas operation (Δ 26, \circ 80 and \diamond 800 L N₂
 22 h⁻¹). Filled gray symbols from Henares et al. [10].

23 Performance of the PP contactor in the operation with N₂ as sweep gas was similar to that
 24 observed with the maximum vacuum of –800 mbar when the liquid flowed through the lumen,

1 with the highest values of RE. However, behavior with the liquid in the shell differed
 2 considerably, and RE using sweep gas was considerable lower, especially at intermediate liquid
 3 flow rate (around 12 L h⁻¹), with a RE of 20% in sweep-gas mode and 60% in vacuum mode (–
 4 800 mbar). The singular low RE at Q_L of 4.1 L h⁻¹ in the vacuum operation and SS mode
 5 (Figure 3a) could be associated with a high liquid mass transfer resistance at the lowest liquid
 6 flow rate due to poor shell-side distribution at low flow rates. Maldistribution of flow, the
 7 presence of stagnant zones, splitting and remixing of streams, and bypassing or channeling
 8 phenomena can occur more frequently in SS than in LS, and can be caused by the nonuniform
 9 fiber distribution and/or fiber deformation [3]. Although the Reynolds values are in the laminar
 10 range, localized turbulence or channeling around the fibers can lead to a higher dependence of
 11 the mass transfer coefficients on the Reynolds number than that typical of a laminar regime.

12 In the vacuum operation (Figure 3a), a sharp decrease in RE was observed for liquid flow rates
 13 higher than or equal to 13.6–16.5 L h⁻¹ depending on pressure vacuum, a phenomenon attributed
 14 to the wetting of the pores that occurs when the pressure difference between liquid and gas side
 15 increases beyond the critical transmembrane pressure (TMP), phenomenon that will be
 16 discussed in the next section 3.3 in the mass transfer analysis. Because the diffusion coefficient
 17 of methane in liquid is much smaller than that in air (Table 3), the membrane transfer coefficient
 18 reduced remarkably when the membrane pores were penetrated by liquid, so the membrane
 19 mass transfer resistance increased as did the observed experimental resistance, which is depicted
 20 in Figure 4a1 against Q_L. The increase in pressure drop with the increase in the liquid velocity
 21 might be the reason for the appearance of wetting for flow rates higher than or equal to 13.6–
 22 16.5 L h⁻¹. Cui et al. [16] observed that the average membrane wetness and wetting rate grew
 23 with the increase in liquid velocity, and demonstrated that the TMP difference grew with an
 24 increase in the liquid flow rate, and this accelerates the movement of liquid into the membrane
 25 pores. Different authors have observed the increase in pore wetting with liquid velocity [10,16–
 26 18]. In the sweep operation, the wetting of the membrane seemed not to appear, probably due to
 27 the high pressure in the gas side that prevented the overcoming of the critical TMP. As a result,
 28 the experimental overall mass transfer resistance increased for the whole liquid flow-rate range
 29 (4b1 and 4b2). These observations are in agreement with the experimentally measured pressure
 30 drop in the contactor (Table 5). As expected, the increase in pressure drop with liquid velocity
 31 was observed, with a higher pressure drop in the LS mode than in the SS mode. However, in the
 32 LS mode, a sharp increase in the pressure drop was recorded for flow rates higher than 13.6 L h⁻¹
 33 ¹. In the SS mode, the increase in the pressure drop was much more moderate, although an
 34 increase was also recorded from 20.4 L h⁻¹.

35 **Table 5.** Liquid pressure drop in the PP membrane contactor with the liquid flowing in the lumen
 36 (LS) and in the shell side (SS).

Q _L , L h ⁻¹	Pressure drop ^a , mbar	
	Lumen Side	Shell side
4.1	39	11
13.6	40	12
16.5	48	11
20.4	53	14
27.2	57	16

^a[10]

1 3.3. Mass transfer analysis

2 The experimental overall mass transfer coefficient ($K_{L,exp}$) of methane was calculated from the
 3 mass balance applied to the liquid phase in the contactor for all experiments (equation 4).
 4 Results are shown in Figure 4, expressed as the experimental mass transfer resistance ($R =$
 5 $(K_{L,exp} A_L)^{-1}$, with A_L value of 0.222 m^2 for lumen-side mode and 0.303 m^2 for shell-side mode).
 6 For the vacuum operation (Figure 4a1 and Figure 4a2), mass transfer resistance increased with
 7 the liquid flow rate in the range $13.6\text{--}20.4 \text{ L h}^{-1}$ due the penetration of water into the pore
 8 structure (wetting operation), which resulted in the predominance of the membrane resistance in
 9 the system. Further increase in the liquid flow rate to 27 L h^{-1} promoted a decrease in the value
 10 of the overall resistance (for example from 3.20×10^5 to $2.70 \times 10^5 \text{ s m}^{-3}$, at -140 mbar). Assuming
 11 that the individual membrane resistance at 27 L h^{-1} was equal or higher than at lower flow rates,
 12 this behavior is probably due to the rise in the individual liquid-side coefficient.

13

14 **Figure 4.** Comparison of the experimental (points) and estimated (lines) mass transfer resistance
 15 in different experiments. a) Vacuum experiments in lumen-side (1) and shell-side (2) mode (Δ –
 16 800 mbar ; \circ -500 mbar ; \diamond -140 mbar). b) Sweep gas experiments in lumen-side (1) and shell-
 17 side (2) mode (Δ 26 , \circ 80 and \diamond $800 \text{ L N}_2 \text{ h}^{-1}$). [$R_L = (k_L A_L)^{-1}$; $R_m = (H k_m A_{ml})^{-1}$; $A_{ml} = 0.260 \text{ m}^2$,
 18 $A_L(\text{LS}) = 0.222 \text{ m}^2$, $A_L(\text{SS}) = 0.303 \text{ m}^2$]

19 The overall mass transfer coefficients in the vacuum operation were calculated taking into
 20 account the concentration of methane in the gas side to estimate the equilibrium liquid
 21 concentration C_L^* (equation (4)). Methane concentration in the gas phase was assumed to be
 22 dependent of the gas pressure, since for every liquid flow rate the RE depended strongly on the
 23 vacuum pressure. Rongwong et al. [13] estimated the methane mole fraction in the gas outlet of
 24 a membrane contactor for different gas side pressures by a mathematical model, which included
 25 simultaneous methane and carbon dioxide desorption. The measured methane gas concentration

1 in our experiments at -500 mbar resulted in $C_G = 74.76 \pm 7.39$ mg L⁻¹, which corresponded to a
2 mole fraction of 0.23, very close to the estimate by Rongwong et al. (~ 0.22). This gas
3 concentration corresponded to an equilibrium liquid concentration C_L^* of 2.53 mg L⁻¹. Thus,
4 values for the pressures of -140 and -800 mbar were obtained from Rongwong et al. [13],
5 estimates resulting in values of C_L^* of 5.82 and 0.51 mg L⁻¹, respectively, which correspond to
6 methane mole fractions of ~ 0.30 and ~ 0.10 . As a result, the experimental resistances values got
7 closed (Figure 4a1), even though the effect of the vacuum pressure was still appreciable,
8 especially for the highest vacuum (-800 mbar).

9 The experimental mass transfer coefficient in the sweep-gas operation was calculated assuming
10 that the concentration of each transferred species in the gas phase was low enough to consider
11 that C_L^* was negligible compared to the actual concentration in the liquid phase ($C_L \gg C_L^*$; $C_L -$
12 $C_L^* \sim C_L$). This assumption was supported experimentally, and it was corroborated by the
13 performance results, since the RE nearly overlapped for different sweep gas flow rates (Figure
14 3b). The resulting mass transfer coefficients were similar to those reported in the literature. In
15 this work, experimental coefficients ranged $[1.94-3.74] \times 10^{-5}$ m s⁻¹ for liquid velocities between
16 0.013 and 0.086 m s⁻¹ in lumen-side mode with sweep gas. Values of $[2.5-3.2] \times 10^{-5}$ m s⁻¹ for
17 velocities between 0.02 and 0.052 m s⁻¹ were obtained with a polyvinylidene fluoride
18 hydrophobically modified membrane [14]. With a commercial PP membrane similar to the one
19 used in this study, values of $[0.09-2.14] \times 10^{-5}$ m s⁻¹ for velocities between 0.0004 and 0.045 m
20 s⁻¹ were reported [11].

21 As expected, the experimental mass transfer resistance in the lumen-side flow was lower than in
22 the shell-side flow. For the vacuum experiments, values ranged from $4.03 \pm 0.93 \times 10^5$ to
23 $1.50 \pm 0.41 \times 10^5$ s m⁻³ ($0.90 \pm 0.21 \times 10^5$ to $0.33 \pm 0.09 \times 10^5$ s m⁻¹) when liquid flows in the
24 lumen-side were 4.1 and 13.6 L h⁻¹, respectively (Figure 4a1), and values ranged from
25 20.6×10^5 to 2.33×10^5 s m⁻³ (6.24×10^5 to 0.71×10^5 s m⁻¹) for the liquid in the shell side
26 (Figure 4a2). For sweep-gas experiments, values ranged from $2.35 \pm 0.28 \times 10^5$ to
27 $1.21 \pm 0.07 \times 10^5$ s m⁻³ ($0.52 \pm 0.06 \times 10^5$ to $0.27 \pm 0.02 \times 10^5$ s m⁻¹) with liquid in the lumen at
28 4.1 and 27.2 L h⁻¹, respectively (Figure 4b1), and from $20.4 \pm 0.8 \times 10^5$ to $5.99 \pm 0.61 \times 10^5$ s m⁻³
29 ($6.18 \pm 0.25 \times 10^5$ to $1.81 \pm 0.19 \times 10^5$ s m⁻¹) for the liquid in the shell side (Figure 4b2).
30 Differences were due to the lower lumen cross-sectional area, which resulted in higher liquid
31 velocities of the liquid in the lumen, so to a higher mass transfer coefficient. These differences
32 were greater at low flow rates, indicating a power-law relation x^{-k} between resistance and liquid
33 velocity.

34 Along with the experimental mass transfer resistance, the estimated resistance is depicted in
35 Figure 4. The system can be described as the sum of the three serial resistances (equation 4):
36 liquid, membrane and gas phases. Resistance of the gas side calculated with equations in Table
37 2 represented less than $7 \times 10^{-3}\%$ of the total resistance in the experiments using sweep gas and
38 was considered negligible. In the experiments with the liquid in the lumen side, the gas
39 resistance represented 1.4%, 1.0% and 0.5% of the total at vacuum pressures of -140 , -500 and
40 -800 mbar, respectively, and was also considered negligible for practical purposes.

41 The liquid phase mass transfer coefficient was estimated with the Lévêque solution (equation
42 11) for the experiments with lumen liquid flow (Figure 4a1 and Figure 4b1), and the resulting
43 mass transfer resistance showed values between 2.54×10^5 and 1.35×10^5 s m⁻³ (0.56×10^5 and
44 0.30×10^5 s m⁻¹) for flow rates of between 4.1 and 27.1 L h⁻¹, respectively. As discussed before,
45 this resistance ($R_L = (k_L A_L)^{-1}$) was predominant in the system and the overall resistance (R_{ov})

1 nearly matched that of the individual liquid phase. For the sweep-gas operation (Figure 4b1),
 2 the estimated resistance described quite accurately the experimental behavior (average relative
 3 error of $11.9 \pm 7.0\%$), with a slight overestimate of the experimental resistance. For the vacuum
 4 operation (Figure 4a1), the estimated resistance was of the same order of magnitude as the
 5 experimental. At the lowest flow rate (4.1 L h^{-1}), the Leveque equation underestimated the
 6 experimental resistances, which could suggest that gas-phase resistance might be playing an
 7 important role, especially at -140 and -500 mbar. At higher flow rates, the increase in the
 8 resistance due to the wetted operation prevented the fitting of the estimation without considering
 9 the increase in the membrane resistance due to pores being partially full of water.

10 Membrane resistance was estimated from the contributions of both molecular and Knudsen
 11 diffusion to the effective diffusion since pore radius was low enough to consider Knudsen
 12 diffusion ($d < 0.1 \mu\text{m}$). To include the wetting phenomena in the mass transfer analyses, a
 13 parameter x was considered, the pore fraction occupied by the liquid [17], and the membrane
 14 coefficient could then be estimated by:

$$\frac{1}{H \cdot k_m} = \frac{1}{H \cdot k_{m,G}} (1 - x) + \frac{1}{k_{m,L}} x \quad (20)$$

15
 16 where $k_{m,G}$ and $k_{m,L}$ are the membrane transfer coefficients with the gas or liquid occupying the
 17 pores, respectively. $k_{m,G}$ is calculated by equation (16) and $k_{m,L}$ as follows:

$$k_{m,L} = \frac{D \cdot \varepsilon}{\tau \cdot l} \quad (21)$$

18 where D is the diffusion coefficient of methane in water (Table 3).

19 Estimated diffusion values are shown in Table 6 for the vacuum and sweep experiments, in
 20 which the resulting mass transfer coefficients and resistances are also included for dry ($x = 0$)
 21 and wetted operation ($x \neq 0$). In our system, the contribution of the Knudsen diffusion due to
 22 collisions of molecules with pore walls was greater than the molecular diffusion, and the
 23 resulting k_m values in dry conditions were in the range $4.28\text{--}5.52 \times 10^{-2} \text{ m s}^{-1}$. As can be
 24 observed in Table 6, the estimated membrane resistance was five orders of magnitude lower
 25 than the experimental resistance when the pores were fully occupied by the gas phase (dry
 26 operation, $x = 0$). The presence of water in 25% of the membrane pores ($x = 0.25$) increased the
 27 resistance by five orders of magnitude, resulting in the same relevance as the liquid resistance.
 28 The increase in experimental resistance for flow rates higher than 16.5 L h^{-1} at -140 and -500
 29 mbar of vacuum pressure and attributed to the wetting could be simulated by considering a pore
 30 fraction occupied by the liquid in the range $0.25\text{--}0.53$. In Table 6, membrane resistance in the
 31 wetting mode with 25% ($x = 0.25$) and 53% ($x = 0.53$) of the pores occupied by the liquid is
 32 also included. Different authors have reported the impact of wetting in the permeate flux due to
 33 reduction of mass transfer. In the absorption of carbon dioxide in water using a PP membrane
 34 contactor similar to the one in this study, estimated liquid penetration lower than 13% resulted
 35 in a resistance of the liquid-filled pores accounting for over 98% of the membrane resistance
 36 and for 20–50% of the total resistance to absorption [17]. For the same application using
 37 commercial membrane contactors of PP and PVDF, the ratio of the membrane resistance
 38 increased sharply from 10 to 70% when only 10% of membrane length was wetted [18]. Values
 39 of wetting percentage of this work (25-53%) are higher than the reported values in the literature
 40 often around 10%, which could indicate that the equations employed overestimated the x value.

Table 6. Membrane mass transfer calculations: Molecular diffusion ($D_{G,m}$), Knudsen diffusion ($D_{G,Kn}$) and effective diffusion ($D_{G,eff}$) of methane in the membrane, and membrane mass transfer coefficient (k_m) and resistance (R_m) in dry ($x = 0$) and wetted ($x \neq 0$) conditions, for the vacuum and sweep-gas operations [$R_m = (Hk_m A_{ml})^{-1}$; $A_{ml} = 0.260 \text{ m}^2$].

	P_{vac} , mbar			Q_{N_2} , L h ⁻¹		
	-140	-500	-800	26	80	800
$D_{G,m}$, m ² s ⁻¹	$2.45 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$4.16 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1.00 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$2.20 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$2.19 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$2.10 \cdot 10^{-5}$
$D_{G,Kn}$, m ² s ⁻¹	$8.37 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$8.37 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$8.37 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$8.37 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$8.37 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$8.37 \cdot 10^{-6}$
$D_{G,eff}$, m ² s ⁻¹	$6.24 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$6.97 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$7.73 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$6.06 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$6.06 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$5.99 \cdot 10^{-6}$
k_m , m s ⁻¹ (x=0)	$4.45 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$4.98 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$5.52 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$4.33 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$4.33 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$4.28 \cdot 10^{-2}$
R_m 10 ⁻⁵ , s m ⁻³ (x=0)	$2.92 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$2.61 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$2.35 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$3.00 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$3.00 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$3.04 \cdot 10^{-5}$
k_m , m s ⁻¹ (x=0.25)	$1.70 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$1.70 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$1.70 \cdot 10^{-6}$	---	---	---
R_m 10 ⁻⁵ , s m ⁻³	0.76	0.76	0.76	---	---	---
k_m , m s ⁻¹ (x=0.53)	$8.03 \cdot 10^{-7}$	$8.03 \cdot 10^{-7}$	$8.03 \cdot 10^{-7}$	---	---	---
R_m 10 ⁻⁵ , s m ⁻³	1.62	1.62	1.62	---	---	---

For the experiments with the liquid in the SS (Figure 4a2 and Figure 4b2), liquid mass transfer coefficient was estimated with equation (15) proposed by Dahuron and Cussler (1988) [36]. For the vacuum operation at -800 mbar (Figure 4a2), the calculated resistance overestimated the experimental at intermediate flow rates (9.0–13.6 L h⁻¹). For sweep-gas operation, the estimated resistance was slightly lower than the experimental, although acceptable agreement was observed considering the standard deviation of the results due to the low RE of shell-side/sweep-gas experiments. Equation (15) better fitted the experimental data than did equation (13), which could indicate the presence of channeling around the fibers in the shell-side mode.

3.4. Long-term operation: impact of fouling

Long-term stability of the membrane is of crucial interest for the final application of the technology since performance of membrane contactors can be adversely affected by wetting and/or fouling. Moreover, when coupling biological reactors and membrane technologies, flux decline due to fouling is one of the main drawbacks of membrane technology. Cleaning strategies might be optimized for the prevention of the use of cleaning chemicals to ensure an economically feasible operation with a long stable life of the system.

Experimental results of the long-term operation of the PP contactor in the LS and the SS mode are presented in Figure 5, as D-CH₄ RE versus time of operation, in which vertical lines indicate the application of the cleaning. In the LS mode (Figure 5a), a total of two operation/cleaning cycles were developed. In the first period, the RE was around 70% over 180 h of operation without any intermediate cleaning, demonstrating high stability performance of the system. A decrease in RE to 50% was recorded after 200 h, which was attributed to fouling of the membrane that included an additional mass transfer resistance. Two consecutive water cleanings of 0.5 and 2 h duration (Water Cleanings 1 and 2, respectively) only restored the initial RE during 50 h of operation (time of operation between Water cleaning 2 and Chemical Cleaning 1 in Figure 5). So, the chemical cleaning protocol was applied in two stages with NaOH (0.5 h)

1 and citric acid (0.5 h) in countercurrent flow (Chemical Cleaning 1). In this way, the initial RE
2 of 70% was restored, as was the time of operation until the next decrease in RE (~200 h of
3 operation). Again, after 590 h, a second chemical cleaning was necessary to recover the RE
4 since Water Cleaning 3 did not succeed.

5 Different behavior was observed in SS mode (Figure 5b). The experiment was carried out with
6 the same liquid flow rate as that in LS mode, resulting in a lower liquid velocity (0.017 m s^{-1} in
7 SS and 0.065 m s^{-1} in LS). The initial RE of around 20% decreased to 10% after only 12 h of
8 operation. This short operation time was attributed to a sudden increase in the suspended solids
9 in the anaerobic effluent due to a partial disintegration of granules. The disintegration of
10 granules in anaerobic reactors has been reported due to different factors such as sole carbon
11 source, insufficient calcium supply, overloading or discontinuous substrate supply [28,46,47]. In
12 our system, most of the disintegrated solids became trapped in the membrane prefilter; however,
13 a small fraction entered the membrane contactor, being responsible for the blocking of some
14 pores and the decrease in the RE. Again, Water Cleaning 1 of 2 h did not recover the
15 performance, but the subsequent Chemical Cleaning 1 successfully restored the RE for 16 h of
16 operation, the longest time of stable operation in continuous SS mode. Chemical Cleaning 2,
17 carried out after 54 h of operation, increased the RE to the initial value (~20%), but the time of
18 operation was slightly reduced to approximately 10 hours between Chemical Cleaning 2 and 3.
19 Further Chemical Cleanings 3 and 4 with a total cleaning time of 6 h (3 h of NaOH + 3 h of
20 citric acid) failed to restore the performance. This could be attributed to the presence of non-
21 reversible fouling, and/or damage to the membrane material that could cause a change in the
22 hydrophobicity. It is important to note that the time of operation without fouling was much
23 lower in SS operation, probably due to the lower liquid velocity, which may favor the deposit of
24 foulants from the biological reactor and promote the appearance of non-reversible fouling. We
25 obtained similar results in the long-term operation of a PDMS membrane contactor for the
26 demethanization of a similar anaerobic effluent [12]. This behaviour differs from the one
27 observed in the filtration process of the membrane bioreactor (MBR) for water purification, in
28 which deposits are brought to the membrane mainly by convective transport and the rate of
29 fouling depends on velocity orthogonal to the surface (the permeate flux). In the membrane
30 contactors for desorption of gases, the membrane acts as a physical support for the gas-liquid
31 interface and the membrane keeps the two phases “in contact” without dispersing one phase into
32 the other. For this particular membrane application, fluid mechanics are dominated by advection
33 rather than convection (as with membrane filtration) thus the effects of concentration
34 polarisation are limited [7].

1

2 **Figure 5.** Performance of the membrane contactor in the long-term operation using N₂ as sweep
 3 gas ($Q_L = 20 \text{ L h}^{-1}$; $Q_{N_2} = 26 \text{ L h}^{-1}$). a) Lumen-side mode, b) Shell-side mode.

4 Possible causes of loss of membrane performance in the long-term operation were investigated.
 5 Water samples from the inlet and outlet of the membrane contactor at different times of the
 6 long-term operation in LS and SS mode were analyzed, and the results are presented in Table 7,
 7 along with the results of the sample before the prefiltration. In the LS mode (Table 7a), the solid
 8 content did not change significantly after prefiltration. After the membrane, a decrease of 30%
 9 in volatile solids was detected, which could indicate the retention of organic matter in the
 10 membrane. In the SS mode, two samples were analyzed at different operation times. The first
 11 one corresponded to 21.5 h of operation, when the first decrease in RE was observed (Table 7b)
 12 and the degranulation episode occurred. In this case, suspended solid content ($<0.7 \mu\text{m}$)
 13 decreased slightly after prefiltration, but the solid content was not altered noticeably after the
 14 membrane contactor. The solid concentrations before prefiltration (i.e. the effluent of the
 15 bioreactor) were the highest of the three samples, confirming the increase in solid content of the
 16 effluent associated with the partial degranulation episode that caused the rapid loss of methane
 17 RE previously mentioned. In spite of the prefiltration of the anaerobic water, the solid
 18 concentration entering the membrane contactor was high at 21.5 hours of operation in shell side
 19 mode, which could cause the rapid loss of methane recovery efficiency (Figure 5b). The
 20 turbidity measurement decreased to a small extent in the outlet, indicating a slight retention of
 21 particulate matter. We obtained similar results in our previous work, with a reduction of
 22 proteins and turbidity at the outlet of a PDMS membrane contactor [12]. The VFAs present in
 23 the inlet of the membrane contactor were practically eliminated, probably removed by sweep
 24 gas along with CH₄ and CO₂. The reduction in soluble COD may also indicate that ethanol in
 25 the inlet of the contactor was partially removed. Soluble polysaccharide content increased

1 significantly after filtration, indicating that some extracellular polymeric substances could be
 2 retained in the filter, and highlighting the importance of regular filter maintenance. The water
 3 characterization after 44.5 h of operation confirmed the results previously observed. No water
 4 parameter changed significantly after the membrane contactor, except the VFA and COD
 5 concentrations. Moreover, analysis of anions (Cl^- , NO_3^- , SO_4^{2-} , PO_4^{3-}) and cations (Na^+ , NH_4^+ ,
 6 K^+ , Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+}) concentrations were carried out in order to elucidate the inorganic fouling,
 7 and results did not show significant differences between the samples (results not shown).

8 **Table 7.** Water characterization before the prefilter (Prefilter), at the membrane inlet (Pre-
 9 membrane) and at the membrane outlet (Post-membrane) in the long-term experiments. a) Lumen-
 10 side mode after 650 h, b) Shell-side mode after 21 h, and c) Shell-side mode after 44 h.

a) Lumen side operation (Sampling at t = 650 h – RE = 70%)			
	Pre-filter	Pre-membrane	Post-membrane
TS (mg L^{-1})	3810 ± 61	3903 ± 66	3777 ± 6
VS (mg L^{-1})	230 ± 8	263 ± 28	160 ± 12
SS (mg L^{-1})	37 ± 12	35 ± 1	37 ± 1
VSS (mg L^{-1})	37 ± 12	30 ± 2	31 ± 4
b) Shell side operation (Sampling at t = 21.5 h – RE = 10%)			
	Pre-filter	Pre-membrane	Post-membrane
TS (mg L^{-1})	4340 ± 598	4146 ± 461	4280 ± 587
VS (mg L^{-1})	716 ± 28	665 ± 41	770 ± 74
SS (mg L^{-1})	112 ± 34	80 ± 24	76 ± 11
VSS (mg L^{-1})	96 ± 10	74 ± 3	74 ± 3
Turbidity (NTU)	85	83	68
VFA ($\text{mg CH}_3\text{COOH L}^{-1}$)	6	6	<LoD*
COD (mg L^{-1})	65 ± 5	67 ± 5	44 ± 2
Polysaccharides, mg L^{-1}	3.7 ± 0.1	7.4 ± 0.2	8.1 ± 0.4
Proteins, mg L^{-1}	---	---	---
c) Shell side operation (Sampling at t = 44.5 h – RE = 18%)			
	Pre-filter	Pre-membrane	Post-membrane
TS (mg L^{-1})	3355 ± 598	3432 ± 461	3516 ± 587
VS (mg L^{-1})	161 ± 15	148 ± 11	149 ± 22
SS (mg L^{-1})	120 ± 24	50 ± 18	56 ± 9
VSS (mg L^{-1})	118 ± 12	48 ± 6	50 ± 9
Turbidity (NTU)	27	24	25
VFA ($\text{mg CH}_3\text{COOH L}^{-1}$)	112	48	5
COD (mg L^{-1})	62 ± 6	64 ± 6	40 ± 2
Polysaccharides, mg L^{-1}	5.3 ± 2.4	5.6 ± 1.2	6.2 ± 0.7
Proteins, mg L^{-1}	3.8 ± 0.3	10.2 ± 0.1	11.2 ± 0.2
<i>*LoD: Limit of Detection</i>			

11
 12 The cleaning effluents of Chemical Cleaning 3 of the experiments in SS mode were also
 13 completely characterized. The chemical cleaning consisted of 2 h cleaning with 2 L of NaOH
 14 followed by 2 h cleaning with 2 L citric acid with continuous recirculation of the solutions. In
 15 this case, the cleaning solutions were divided into four aliquots of 0.5 L, recirculated for 0.5 h

1 and then analyzed. Results of the parameters showing important variations are presented in
2 Figure 6. Results showed an increase in concentration of suspended solids (SS) in the NaOH
3 solution, which were mainly inorganic (25% volatile suspended solids, VSS) (Figure 6a). The
4 highest concentration was recorded after 0.5 h of cleaning, with a smooth decrease until values
5 higher than the initial solution concentration. The peak of suspended solids was accompanied by
6 an increase in turbidity. The citric acid solution removed a much greater quantity of suspended
7 solids, but in this case mainly organic (99% VSS). In this case, turbidity measurements were
8 very low. Again, a high peak of around 900 mg VSS L⁻¹ was observed after 0.5 h, and the
9 suspended solid concentration remained at a high value of around 380 mg SS L⁻¹ after 2 h
10 cleaning. Regarding the soluble fraction, NaOH cleaning also cleaned out polysaccharides and
11 proteins, suggesting the presence on the membrane surface of extracellular polymeric
12 substances and other organic foulants generated from the cellular lysis inside the bioreactor,
13 which could be the cause of the loss of efficiency. After 2 hours of cleaning, concentration of
14 polysaccharides in the NaOH solution was of 8 mg L⁻¹, higher than the concentration of the
15 initial solution (< 2 mg L⁻¹) (Figure 6b). These results suggested that the cleaning did not
16 remove completely the organic foulants attached to the membrane, and this may be the cause of
17 the rapid loss of performance after this cleaning. Thus, a new chemical cleaning (number 4) was
18 carried out but the performance did not recover, confirming the presence of non-reversible
19 fouling.

20 Even though the analyses of water samples during the long-term operation did not show any
21 significant variation to explain the nature of the fouling, cleaning solution analysis revealed that
22 fouling could be associated with both organic and inorganic foulants. NaOH solution washed
23 out inorganic solids, polysaccharides and proteins, whereas citric acid solution washed out a
24 large quantity of organic solids. A higher concentration of organic foulants were washed out,
25 confirming that the fouling was characterized mainly by extracellular polymeric substances and
26 other biofoulants coming from the anaerobic reactor.

27 The analyses of water at the inlet and outlet of the contactor during the long-term experiments
28 did not provide conclusive results about the nature of the fouling, probably due to the low
29 variation of some parameters along with the low accuracy of some analytical methods. Instead,
30 follow-up on the concentration of potential foulants in the cleaning solutions is recommended as
31 an experimental protocol, not only to elucidate the character of the fouling but also to optimize
32 the cleaning procedure.

1

2 **Figure 6.** Results of the characterization of NaOH and citric acid cleaning solutions with time of
 3 Chemical Cleaning 3 of the long-term experiment in shell-side mode: a) Suspended Solids (SS),
 4 Volatile Suspended Solids (VSS), Turbidity; b) Soluble Total Organic Carbon (TOC),
 5 polysaccharides and proteins.

6 An additional experiment was carried out to confirm the presence of biofouling. A solution of
 7 similar composition to the feed of the anaerobic reactor (i.e. ethanol as organic substrate and a
 8 mixture of nutrients) was fed into the membrane contactor in a closed loop over 4 h with no
 9 sweep gas or vacuum pressure. Concentration of ethanol at the beginning and end of the test
 10 was measured as TOC concentration. A blank test with the membrane after chemical cleaning
 11 resulted in an ethanol removal of 5%, which can be explained by ethanol evaporation or
 12 transference to the gas phase. The same assay in the presence of confirmed fouling (before
 13 cleaning) resulted in a considerably higher ethanol removal of 28%. In the absence of sweep gas
 14 and vacuum, this could indicate that ethanol biodegradation occurred to some extent inside the
 15 contactor affected by fouling, suggesting the presence of biological degrading activity and
 16 hence the biofouling. Although also physical or chemical sorption of ethanol onto the inorganic
 17 and/or organic foulants could be involved in the ethanol depletion, previous studies suggest that
 18 most of the biomass and potential inorganic deposits have affinity to water in ethanol/water

1 mixtures and almost no ethanol might be adsorbed [48,49]. Further investigation in fouling
2 characterization is necessary to elucidate the predominant mechanisms.

3 Results demonstrate that a cleaning strategy to prevent operational failure due to fouling is
4 necessary. During the short-term experiments, a daily cleaning with deionized water in
5 countercurrent flow for 30 min was applied. This water backwash cleaning method was found to
6 maintain the methane RE over 3510 h of operation in LS mode and 1620 h in SS mode without
7 fouling [28]. Since this method does not require chemicals (i.e. does not cause secondary
8 pollution), is cost-saving and is easy to perform, it would be recommended as the regular
9 cleaning method.

10 **4. Conclusions**

11 The use of a PP membrane contactor for the recovery of dissolved methane from anaerobic
12 effluents has been demonstrated as an efficient and promising technology. Higher removal
13 efficiencies can be obtained using vacuum pressure or sweep gas in the gas side, and good
14 performance in long-term operation may be achieved by prefiltration of the effluent for
15 particulate matter removal and by using a preventive cleaning based on a daily water
16 countercurrent wash-out.

17 In the vacuum operation, pore wetting was detected when increasing the liquid flow rate at
18 intermediate values, probably due to the increase in the pressure drop. The liquid mass transfer
19 resistance was the most relevant in the system, especially during the dry operation (non-wetted
20 mode). As expected, the membrane resistance gained importance in the wetted operation, and an
21 estimated wet pore fraction of between 0.25 and 0.53 could simulate the experimental results in
22 the wetted operation. The use of nitrogen as sweep gas resulted in a more efficient and stable
23 operation. Higher removal efficiencies were obtained in lumen-side mode, and pore wetting was
24 not detected, probably due to the lower TMP. No influence of the gas flow rate was observed.

25 Long-term operation was performed in the lumen-side and shell-side modes with the same
26 liquid flow rate. Higher operation time in lumen-side mode was observed, of 180 h, against 16 h
27 in shell-side mode. Water cleaning was not effective when fouling had already affected the RE,
28 and chemical cleanings were necessary to restore the performance. Analyses of cleaning
29 samples for characterization of the shell-side fouling revealed that volatile and non-volatile
30 suspended solids were washed out. Polysaccharides and proteins were also cleaned out from the
31 membrane contactor, suggesting the presence of extracellular polymeric substances. Thus, the
32 presence of both inorganic and organic foulants seemed to be responsible for the performance
33 decline. Ethanol biodegradation in the membrane contactor was suggested, and hence the
34 biological nature of the fouling. Based on experimental results of the short-term experiments, a
35 daily water cleaning of 30 min is proposed to prevent fouling and to extend the operational life.

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